

**WORD-FORMATION IS ONE WAY TO ENHANCE ENGLISH
TERMINOLOGY.**

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Abstract

This article is dedicated to the research of word-formation is one of the means of extending the English terminology to the ways in which new words are produced, and the criteria that determine their adoption into the language are typically taken for granted by the ordinary speaker.

Key words: language, investigate, relationship, new, adjective, concept, productive.

Our essay gives an excellent summary of some of the most important word generation mechanisms present in the English language. Word-formation refers to the processes of developing new terminology in a language. This is not to say that word formation exclusively discusses how words are formed based on notions that are novel to us as present speakers of the language. It also does not imply that we "form" these new phrases in our minds every time we use them. Instead, it studies previous and contemporary methods for producing words in languages; some of these methods may no longer be in use. The -ly in friendly or ghostly, for example, is no longer utilised to construct new adjectives. However, understanding how a new word was developed at one time in the past helps us recognise the link with older words. For example, we can observe that the term ghostly was created from the stem ghost and the ending -ly. Other ways, such as the ending -ness explained in the article, are still used often in English. It's also worth noting that rules like the -ness rule for establishing new words are said to as productive since we can currently build new linguistic forms with them. The processes by which new words are produced, as well as the criteria that control their admission into the language, are largely taken for granted by most people. It is not required to grasp a word's construction, whether it is simple or complicated, that is, if it can be broken down into two or more parts. We are able to employ a new term once we understand what item or concept it refers to. Of course, some words are more "transparent" than others. For example, in the phrases unfathomable and incomprehensible, we see the classic pattern of negative prefix +transitive word + adjective-forming suffix, which is used to build numerous words of similar structure. Knowing the pattern, we can readily infer their meanings - "cannot be formed" and "cannot be described" - yet we are not shocked to find additional similar-looking phrases, such as unfashionable and unfavourable, for which our analysis will not work. Many linguists believe that the question of word production has gotten little attention from descriptive grammarians of English or researchers working in the field of general linguistics until recently. As a collection of several processes (compounding, affixation, conversion, backformation, etc.) about which general conclusions are difficult to make. Word-formation is the area of lexicology that focuses on the patterns that a language—in this example, the English language—uses to create new words. It should go without saying that word-formation is limited to terms that can be examined from both a structural and semantic perspective. There is no space for the examination of the basic phrase in it. Therefore, **writer, displeas, atom-free**, etc. are relevant to word-formation, but **to write, to please, atom, free** are not. As

with other linguistic phenomena, word-formation may be examined from both a synchronic and diachronic perspective. It is important to distinguish between these two methods because the linguist looks into the modern system of word construction while looking into the history of word building diachronically. To illustrate the difference of approach we shall consider affixation. When a word is derived, it is more complicated both structurally and semantically than when it is simple; diachronically, it is developed from another term. Regardless of whether a derived word was derived from a simple stem or not, on the synchronic plane, it is considered to have a more complicated structure than its linked simple word. Determining the constituents' placement within the language's overall structural system is vital, even when analysing and describing word-formation synchronically only involves extracting the pertinent structural elements from a word and describing it in terms of word-formation. As a result, productivity of a derivative kind cannot be disregarded in the explanation. When the need arises, some of the word-formation techniques used in modern English can be used to create new words; these are known as productive word-formation techniques; other word-formation techniques, on the other hand, are deemed non-productive or unproductive because they are unable to create new words. For instance, since the time of Old English, affixation has been a fruitful method of word formation. The several forms and methods of word formation that have been cited in the linguistic literature on the subject are listed below. Affixation is a fairly popular method of word formation. A bound morpheme is said to be affixed when it is joined to a free morpheme, or stem. The bound morpheme might appear in the centre of the stem, after, or before the stem. Prefixes (from the Latin pre-=before) are affixes that come before the stem. Suffixes are words that come after the stem; the word comes from the Latin sub-, which means under. Additionally, infixes are the affixes that go in the centre. In English, prefixes and suffixes are often used. For instance, prefixes like sad, unlock, preexist, uncertain, lockable, or gorgeous might be used with related suffixes. We also want to emphasise that an affix's proximity to a stem infix does not increase when many affixes are combined in a row. As an illustration, the ending -ist in realistic is not an infix but a suffix. Generally speaking, affixation is the process of creating new words by adding derivational attaches to several kinds of bases. The stems of words making up derived words generated by affixation may come from one or more applications of the word-formation rule. A word cluster engage in varying degrees of derivational linkages. The zero words with a homonymous stem are considered simple words due to their degree of derivation. In the shape of a word and frequently with a root-morpheme (e.g., atom, eager, devoted, terror, etc.). Words that are derived from two successive coining stages have the second degree of derivation, among other examples (atomically, hurriedly, devotionally, etc.). Affixation is separated into suffixation and prefixation in accordance with the classification of derivational affixes into suffixes and prefixes. The last stage of derivation, which establishes the nature of the derived word with its motivating source unit, naturally makes the distinction between prefixal and suffixal derivatives. Examples of this stage of derivation are unjust (un+just), justify (just+-ify), arrange (arrange + -ment), and non-smoker (non + smoker). Words that are frequently classified as prefixal-suffixal derivatives include reappearance, unreasonable, and denationalise. According to R.S. Ginzburg, this categorization only matters when considering the individual morphemes that make up these words, or when examining them from a morphemic analysis perspective. Derivational analysis indicates that these terms are mostly suffixal or prefixal derivatives, for example, subatomic = sub- +(atom+ -ic), unreasonable = un- + (reason+ -able), and denationalise. There are key distinctions between suffixal and

prefixal derivatives that have been identified by a thorough analysis of several examples. Prefixation is mostly typical of verb creation in modern English, whereas suffixation is primarily characteristic of noun and adjective construction. The distinction also stems from the part that various meanings play in the suffix and prefix's semantic structures. The part of the speech meaning has a much greater significance in suffixes as compared to prefixes which possess it in a lesser degree. Due to it, a prefix may be confined to one part of speech as, for example, *enslave*, *engage*, *unbutton* or may function in more than one part of speech as *over-* in *overkind*, *overfeed*, *overestimation*. Unlike prefixes, suffixes as a rule function in any one part of speech often forming a derived stem of a different part of speech as compared with that of the base, e.g. *careless-care*; *suitable-suit*, etc. Furthermore, it is necessary to point out that a suffix closely knit together with a base forms a fusion retaining less of its independence than a prefix which is as a general rule more independent semantically, e.g. *reading* - : the act of one who reads"; "ability to read"; and to *re – red – “to red again”*.

Compounding is another typical method of word construction. It is so productively utilised in technical languages that it is most likely the most prevalent in modern English. The act of compounding involves combining two or more separate words to form a single word. Numerous instances are provided, all of which are simple to locate in the actual world. "Itself" is an example of a compound noun. I discovered the following instances of what I found: starting intersect point, column centerline grid, default Project Architect support directory, exit light fixture symbol, and remove project menu. In the final case, the verb "delete" is used. Suppletion is the next method of word construction.

Suppletion is a bit tricky but is also rare in English. It is the outcome of a past procedure that has been preserved throughout time. In a nutshell, there have always been two terms in the language that have comparable meanings and are usually employed in distinct dialects. The two terms eventually combined to form a single paradigm. For instance, there were two words for "to be" in an older version of the English language: *wesan* and *eom*. The paradigm for to be was created by combining these two into one. It is not necessary to completely comprehend this process in order to teach English, though, as substitution is rare and its forms are memorably understood.

Blending: Blends are made up of two words combined into one: *smog* from *smoke* and *fog*, *brunch* from *breakfast* and *lunch*, and *chortle* from *laugh* and *snort*. Blends are often the beginning of one word and the end of another. (This blend was created by Lewis Carroll, who also provided numerous other intriguing blend examples in his poem "Jabberwocky." Carroll referred to them as "portmanteau words.")

Borrowing: Foreign terms are always being "borrowed" onto other languages, especially to accompany new ideas, inventions, products, and so on. When speakers imitate a word from a foreign language and at least partly adapt it in sound or grammar to their native speech patterns, the process is called "borrowing", and the word thus borrowed is a "loanword". A few examples: *alcohol* (Arabic), *boss* (Dutch), *croissant* (French), *lilac* (Persian), *piano* (Italian), *pretzel* (German), *robot* (Czech), *tycoon* (Japanese), *yoghurt* (Turkish), *zebra* (Bantu). A special type of borrowing is described as "loan-translation" or "*calque*". In this process, there is a direct translation of the elements of a word into the borrowing language. For example: English *hot dogs* becomes Spanish *perros calientes*, English *skyscraper* becomes French *le gratte – ciel*.

Backformation: Backformation is a word formed by subtraction of a real or supposed affix from an already existing longer word (as *burgle* from *burglar*) Backformation is a term

borrowed from diachronic linguistics. Backformation makes use of a process called *analogy* to derive new words, but in a rather backwards manner, that is from an older word that is mistakenly assumed to be a derivative of it. For example, we have words such as *revision* and *revise* and *supervision* and *supervise*. *Revision* is formed by regular derivation from *revision+ion*. When *television* was invented, the verb *televise* was back formed on the basis of analogy with *revision* and *revise*, that is: Revision: revise: television: X [Examples from Merriam – Webster’s collegiate dictionary. Merriam – Webster, Incorporated: 193]. To cite another example, the verb *donate* was formed on the basis of pairs such as *creation – create*. We borrowed *donation* from French and back formed *donate*. Creation: create: donation: X Another example, in the original the final consonant [-z] of *pease* is not, as it seems to the ear to be, the English plural suffix –s. It is, in fact, not a suffix at all. But by the 17th century, *pease* was mistaken for a plural, and a new singular, *pea*, was derived from a word that was itself a singular, precisely as if we were to derive a form **chee* from *cheese* just as we have *one pea*, *two peas*. One very regular source of back-formed verbs in English is based on the pattern: *worker-work*. The assumption seems to have been that if there is a noun ending in –*er* (or something close in sound), then we can create a verb for what noun –*er* does. Hence, an *editor* must *edit*, a *sculptor* must *sculpt*, and *burglars*, *peddlers*, and *swindlers* must *burgle*, *peddle* and *swindle*.

Acronyms: these words are formed by taking the initial sounds or letters of the words of a phrase and uniting them into a combination that is itself pronounceable as a separate word. Thus *NATO* is an acronym for *North Atlantic treaty Organization*, *laser* for *light amplification through the stimulated emission of radiation*, and *radar* for *radio detection and ranging*.

Clipping: Frequently we shorten words without paying attention to the derivational morphology of the word (or related terms). We see here again the element of reduction, already seen in blending. *Exam* has been clipped from *examination*, *dorm* from *dormitory*, and both *taxi* and *cab* from *taxi cab* (itself clipping from *taximeter cabriolet*). Because clipping often ignores lexical and morphemic boundaries and cuts instead in the middle of a morpheme, we end up creating new morphemes and enriching the stock of potential building material for making other terms.

Coinage: terms may also be created without using any of the methods described above and without employing any other term or word parts already in existence; that is, they may be created out of thin air. Such brand names as *Xerox*, *Kodak*, and *Exxon* were made up without reference to any other word, as were the common words *pooch* and *snob*. Also called “root creation”.

Conversion or Functional Shift: conversion, one of the principal ways of forming words in Modern English, is highly productive in replenishing the English wordstock with new terms. A new word may be created simply by shifting from one part of speech to another one without changing the form of the term – without adding any affixes. *Laugh*, *run*, *buy*, *steal* are used as nouns as well as verbs, while *position*, *process*, *contrast* are nouns from which verbs have been formed.

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